

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE NATIONAL SYSTEM AND THE INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING IN ADOLESCENCE

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Annotation: *At the heart of the reforms being carried out in the new Uzbekistan today are young people and their intellectual potential. The President of our country said, "We must pay special attention to the active participation of young people in the democratic process in the life of our country, to increase their political and social potential."¹ This article discusses the issues of inculcating the national spirit in the lives of adolescents, the impact of advertising on their psychology.*

Keywords: *Teenager, advertising, national system, potential, person, effect.*

INTRODUCTION

It is impossible to imagine the life of a modern person without advertising. Advertising is a dynamic, rapidly transforming sphere of human activity. For many years, being a constant companion of man, she changes with him. Being an important link between the producer and the consumer, advertising contributed to the development of society. It has

always been one of the important levers that stimulate the production process, the improvement of manufactured goods, and in this capacity it acts not only as an "engine of trade", but also as a kind of "engine of progress"².

Advertising has flooded TV screens, streets, newspapers and magazines. Advertising uses the media to spread its ads regarding consumer

¹ Sh.M.Mirziyoev The work of a nation with great intentions is also great, its life is bright and its future is prosperous. Tashkent. NMIU "Uzbekistan" 2019. P-386

² M.Kahhorova Inheritance is an important factor in the formation of moral values. F.f.n ... diss. - T.: O'zMU. 2011. - 162 p.

products, various organizations and policies. Advertising is a deliberate attempt to influence human behavior. It belongs to the external manifestations of our everyday life, our daily life, being an integral part of the world around us. Gradually, it penetrates deeply into our subconscious.

This is especially true for adolescents, who, due to their age characteristics, are characterized by increased excitability, impulsiveness, imbalance, and reckless actions and deeds. Advertising has a strong impact on the formation and development of attitudes to the outside world and reality, as well as the personal relationships of adolescents, since it is at this age that the psyche is formed, which is most susceptible to external influences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It should not be forgotten that in historical periods, one of the spiritual values is replaced by another, complements, enriches, develops, that is, without denying the old at all, but

giving up its unnecessary aspects and creating new development.

So, even today, the most important basis for the upbringing of the new generation is to rely on the experience of the older generation, to continue the moral values based on inheritance, in accordance with the wise thoughts of our ancestors. When each higher stage of development is "inherited" from the lower stage, it does not deny the former, but with its help it is enriched and developed. Denial, by its very nature, implies not only the end of antiquity, but also the further development, while preserving the progressive positive achievements achieved in the earlier stages.

The premises of modern advertising have been accompanying a person for many centuries. For a long time, these forms were not recognized as an expression of one phenomenon. They lived on their own. Some of these forms can be considered the prototype of modern types of advertising. Namely:

- Rock paintings, in which we find information about the place of hunting and its results, can be

considered the starting point of modern outdoor advertising.

- "Image" advertising was also present, as a person has always sought to stand out among his own kind, using various elements of clothing.

- And of course, the most common transmission of information is oral transmission, which in the modern sense is word-of-mouth advertising.

All this can be described as primitive advertising. Its further development completely depended on the development of both society as a whole and the productive forces in particular. It should be emphasized that it was the technical and scientific achievements of mankind, such as the invention of printing, the discovery of electricity, radio, human spaceflight, the computer revolution, etc., that became the basis for the means of distributing modern advertising.

Today it is simply impossible to walk down the street and not come across an abundance of all kinds of

advertising, it is everywhere: on billboards, posters, leaflets, stands, poles, on transport, in newspapers, on television, on radio, etc. Advertising is made up of many elements, its goals and objectives can be different, as well as the options for its creation, as well as the channels through which it is distributed. And there are many classifications of modern advertising. The most common of them is by the method of distribution - television, print, radio, video and film advertising, advertising on transport, outdoor advertising, etc. are distinguished here.

In addition to television commercials, advertising appeals to schoolchildren and teenagers through children's magazines, posters and signs on the streets, through toys in the form of favorite characters, through images of characters on food and industrial products. Finally, through social networks and virtual clubs, children like to feel that they belong to a certain circle³.

³ M.Kahhorova Inheritance is an important factor in the formation of moral values. F.f.n ... diss. - T .: O'zMU. 2011. - 103 p.

Advertising on television is the most expensive, most massive and prestigious form of advertising. Its efficiency is very high. It is explained by the synthesis of two types of influence on a person - visual and auditory. A person perceives advertising in the press only visually, advertising on the radio - only through hearing, but television advertising is perceived by both channels. That is why it is so effective, and advertisers do not spare money on it. Television can influence not only the consciousness, but also the subconscious of a person. That is why the effectiveness of TV - advertising leaves no doubt.

Moreover, children and adolescents are influenced not only by advertising aimed directly at them, but also by advertising designed for adults. In the daytime, there are advertisements for movies containing scenes of violence, in many commercials there is an emphasis on the increased sexuality of the

character, and without special need, - all this causes understandable fears.

For example, cigarette advertising may be a greater risk factor for children than smoking family members or peers, and may even undermine the educational influence of parents; and of all TV ads, half are those promoting unhealthy food products, primarily sugary breakfast cereals and high-calorie snacks; 20% of fast food ads promise a free toy with the food.

Very often, extremely thin models are shown, which can lead to low self-esteem and mental disorders up to anorexia in adolescent girls.

Teenagers today are in a situation of choice, and often this situation is very difficult. They have to choose between different views and different ideas, and, which is especially difficult, form their own picture of the world⁴.

Among the commercials that schoolchildren remember more than others are advertisements for energy drinks, Kinder Surprise, Coca-Cola,

⁴Dudareva A., "Psychology in advertising - Attention! Children!" August 24, 2007

Skittles, cosmetics, movie advertisements, as well as advertisements about sports. When asked why this particular advertisement was remembered, the answers were as follows: “funny”, “memorable song”, “interesting plot”, “touching”, “bright”. In addition to the most preferred, teenagers also named the least liked commercials that cause a negative attitude. For schoolchildren, these are various dandruff shampoos, advertisements for household products. At the same time, the explanations were as follows: “uninteresting”, “unfunny”, “unpleasant”, “boring”.

Although many people are disgusted by advertising with its obtrusiveness, duration, and frequent repetitions, they still answer the question: “If you had a choice - what to buy: an advertised product or not, what would you buy?” the majority of respondents answered that they would buy the advertised product.

During the analysis of the questionnaires, a direct connection between the value orientations of

adolescents and their attitude to advertising was determined.

Among those who expressed distrust of advertising, the values of interpersonal communication, such as friendship, family happiness, parents and relatives, prevail. This may indicate the presentation of television advertising for these adolescents as an unimportant factor in their lives and the desire to avoid its influence, i.e. advertising for the vast majority of these adolescents is not perceived as a "model" of interpersonal relationships.

The presence in the answers of some students of such priority values as a computer, a mobile phone suggests that adolescents mistakenly develop the opinion that only by purchasing advertised goods can one become like a person who succeeds in life. Therefore, probably, some would also like to have a big house, a car, a lot of money.

When asked if my peers would like to follow any advertisement, only 3% answered yes. But this is not just advertising, but social - advertising for helping children and the disabled.

The study showed that television advertising, of course, affects adolescents, plays a decisive role in shaping consumer preferences. Some schoolchildren recognize commercials by their visuals, sound accompaniment, reproduce individual statements, expressions, melodies. However, the majority critically perceive television advertising, argue their perception of advertising products.

Thus, we can conclude that the results of advertising exposure are ambiguous, far from always negative, which directly depends on the age, level of mental development of a teenager, his interests and life goals⁵.

CONCLUSION

Advertising in modern society extends its influence not only to the economic sphere of human relations, but also affects the value choice and psychological comfort of the individual. Teenagers, compared with adults, are not able to effectively resist the effects of advertising. But, despite the results of the survey, one cannot

but say that it is almost impossible to deceive a thinking person who has his own opinion. Teenagers understand the meaninglessness of some advertising and can analyze what they are offered and realize whether they need this product or this service.

Based on the research data, we can conclude that advertising affects the psyche of a teenager, but you should not be afraid of this, since for most adolescents who have a negative attitude towards it, advertising is only a carrier of information about the world around them, without affecting the values. This indicates a fairly high level of their morality, which is greatly influenced by both the existing social environment, the system of foundations of a provincial city, and the system of educational work of the school.

It is impossible to live completely without advertising. This is understood by both teenagers and adults. But you need to do everything necessary to ensure that advertising is of high quality, so that it does not

⁵ Mokshantsev R.I. Psychology of advertising. - M., 2010.P.45

throw dust in the eyes of the buyer, but gives reliable information.

Reforms in the education system are an important step in increasing the intellectual potential of young people so that they can participate fully in socio-cultural development. For example, a number of decrees and decisions on the development of the education system in the country have

been adopted, creating the basis for the orientation of a harmoniously developed generation in the field of sports and increasing their intellectual potential. This, in turn, creates ample opportunities for the manifestation of the intellectual potential of young people as a result of national development.

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